

Project Deliverable Information Sheet

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List of participants

Participant No.	Participant organisation name	Country
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2	Institut Laue-Langevin (ILL)	France
3	European XFEL (XFEL.EU)	Germany
4	The European Spallation Source (ESS)	Sweden
5	Extreme Light Infrastructure Delivery Consortium (ELI-DC)	Belgium
6	Central European Research Infrastructure Consortium (CERIC-ERIC)	Italy
7	EGL Foundation (EGL.eu)	The Netherlands

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PaNOSC website

The PaNOSC Website – <https://www.panosc.eu> – is the main communication and dissemination tool of the PaNOSC project. It contains all the information supplied, recommended and/or required by the PaNOSC project and its partners, to inform and keep all stakeholders up to date about project’s goals, achievements, services and training material developed. Content is structured organically and in compliance with the general requirements of accessibility and usability. The web design is responsive, i.e. it is easily manageable and optimized for the use on mobile devices and popular platforms, as well as compatible with all major browsers.

All software deployed for the construction and maintenance of the Website, as well as the Website’s content and the <https://www.panosc.eu> domain are property of the PaNOSC Consortium.

PaNOSC website’s structure

PaNOSC website’s content

The website’s homepage provides a brief description of the project and gives an overview of its main objectives. Latest news and upcoming events are clearly highlighted, together with the latest social media posts published on the PaNOSC Twitter account. Finally, all partners and PaNOSC related projects are visible in the sliders at the bottom of the homepage. Content is organized into seven main sections, as further described below:

- **About us**

This section describes the main scope of the project, with details about the activities carried out in each single work package and the related deliverables. Contact details of WP leaders can be find under the “Contacts” section, which also includes an online contact form for enquiries sent through the website, which will be directed to contact@panosc.eu. Job offers published by partners to recruit personnel in the frame of

the project will be published in a dedicated area under this section.

The screenshot shows the 'Contacts' page of the PaNOSC website. The page has a dark blue header with the PaNOSC logo and navigation menu. The main content area is white and contains a contact form and a list of Work Package (WP) leaders.

Contacts

For general inquiries about PaNOSC please submit an issue to this project or send an email to contact@panosc.eu

To contact the management board of PaNOSC, please contact management@panosc.eu

Name *

First* Last*

Email *

Institution/Company

Your message *

Privacy *

I hereby agree to the PaNOSC [privacy policy](#)*

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- **Data Policy**

This section includes the definition of FAIR principles, as well as the description of the steps envisaged in the frame of the project, towards the fine-tuning of a common data policy for PaN facilities.

- **Services**

This section allows PaN users to find and access all services developed throughout the project in the fields of data storage, data analysis, and simulation data systems. In addition, PaN data catalogues and the PaN software catalogue will be accessible from

this section. The Help Desk service will allow submitting enquiries on all services to PaNOSC partners through an online contact form.

photon and neutron
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Contacts Search PaNOSC 🔍

About ▾
Data policy ▾
Services ▾
Developments ▾
Training ▾
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EOSC

[Home](#) > [Services](#)

Services

Data Catalogue

Search, find and access data from PaN sources across the federated, cross-disciplinary and cross-border data catalogues infrastructure. Get easy access to the broadest sets of data from the diverse catalogues of European photon and neutron facilities, through the PaNOSC data catalogues using the federated search engine compatible with OpenAIRE.

[More info →](#)

Data Storage

Search, find and access data from PaN sources across the federated, cross-disciplinary and cross-border data catalogues infrastructure, and access scientific open data remotely.

[More info →](#)

Data Analysis

Analyse, use and re-use raw data from PaN facilities, using Jupyter notebooks based data analysis services. Get new scientific insights using technique specific notebook recipes with the advanced technology for remote and cloud access via a user-friendly interface.

[More info →](#)

Simulation Data System

Enter PaN cloud-based virtual facility and access the available simulation data services to rapidly prototype and execute (both experimental and simulation) data workflows from designing your beamline (using OASYS) to simulating the data to be produced to better plan your experiment and/or understand the results.

[More info →](#)

Pan Software Catalogue

Access the PaN software catalogue linked to the analysis and simulation software used in PaN facilities. Find documentation, links and complete examples of data sets and practical information about the scientific instruments used to collect them.

[More info →](#)

Help Desk

Contact us for any question or clarification about the services developed for the PaN user community.

[More info →](#)

- **Developments**

This section describes and lists all developments, which will be set-up and released during the project.

- **Training**

This section will link to the project's e-learning platform, and will make available useful training material, including the video tutorials developed in WP8. A calendar will showcase all upcoming training events organized in the frame of the project.

- **Materials**

In this section, useful material, such as presentations and publications related to the project, will be published, as well as articles and interviews with “women in science”, to describe their use of and experience with open data. Use cases of the services developed in the project will also be presented.

- **News & Events**

This area of the website will be regularly updated with information about the latest news and developments of the project, its main achievements, as well as about the upcoming events and opportunities.

[Home](#) [News](#)

News

Filter by year ▾

OASYS School 14-16 May, 2019 - [View more](#)

Published on 21 May 2019

The ESRF welcomed the 1st OASYS School

14-16 May 2019, Grenoble – France Researchers and engineers from eight light sources in Europe and the Americas have met at the ESRF for the first OASYS School, a hands-on meeting to modelling synchrotron beamlines using OASYS (ORange Synchrotron Suite). This user-friendly graphical environment developed by Luca Rebuffi and Manuel Sanchez del Rio incorporate well [...]

[Read →](#)

Published on 8 May 2019

New PaNOSC calendar with EOOSC related events

We now have a PaNOSC Calendar! Find out more about past and upcoming all PaNOSC and related events .

[Read →](#)

Published on 31 January 2019

PaNOSC at the ESFRI RIs and EOOSC Workshop

Rudolf Dimper, Head of the Technical Infrastructure Division at the ESRF, presented PaNOSC at the ESFRI RIs and EOOSC workshop, held in London on 30 January 2019. The event focused on the relationship between ESFRI, ESFRI Research Infrastructures (RIs) and the European Open Science Cloud (EOOSC) stakeholders, to foster the optimal integration of ESFRI RIs [...]

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- EOSC
Direct link to the www.eosc-portal.eu website.

PaNOSC website's update

CERIC-ERIC, WP9 leader, is responsible for the maintenance and update of the project's website. All partners and WP leaders will contribute to it by providing updates on the work packages' advancements, as well as on attended events and results achieved. The only personal data collected through the website are those inserted by users sending enquiries through the online contact form – i.e., name, surname and email –, which are collected by the project coordinator, ESRF, who is responsible for their processing, as further specified in the website's privacy policy.